

TC FOR BE

TRANSFORMATIVE CHANGE
FOR BIODIVERSITY & EQUITY

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Tools for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) of the TCforBE project

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Overview

The Transformative Change for Biodiversity and Equity (TCforBE) project (2022 – 2026) aims to support transdisciplinary research to co-generate transformative change pathways in the context of telecoupled agrifood systems. It is engaging diverse stakeholders and exploring plural perspectives within the EU and partner countries of Cameroon, Colombia, and Kenya, including EU and national policymakers and Indigenous Peoples and local communities. The project seeks to strengthen stakeholder capacity on transformative change pathways leading to enhanced biodiversity and equity outcomes. Work package (WP) 7 of the project is concerned with management, dissemination and communication to ensure successful implementation to maximise the project's potential.

In deliverable 7.7, a set of tailored Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) tools, materials and activities are being developed. These include dissemination (e.g. peer-reviewed publications, conferences, meetings, participation in conferences), communications (e.g. webpage, social media, templates for policy briefs and press releases, brand elements such as project logo and colour palette etc.). These outputs differ in aims (e.g. some are to inform, to engage or co-create). The DEC tools, materials and activities also serve to grow the TCforBE network and facilitate knowledge sharing on transformative approaches.

In this report, we provide an update on DEC tools developed and describe their respective purposes in line with the aims listed above.

TCforBE Project Summary

Demand for agricultural commodities from EU agrofood systems is driving land use change in biodiversity-rich countries in the Global South, leading to major biodiversity losses. Globalisation processes have led to increases in EU imports of commodities such as soya and palm oil. EU trade has become increasingly 'telecoupled', i.e. characterised by distant, coupled human and natural systems via highly inequitable global value chains, which have extensive socioeconomic and environmental impacts.

Tackling the EU's global biodiversity footprint is a top EU policy priority. Transformative change pathways are needed for safe and just transitions, but there are plural perspectives on what might constitute transformative change for food territories and systems, including telecoupled ones, and how to achieve it. New EU policies, such as Farm to Fork, may significantly re-shape agro-food trade between the EU and producer countries, with a range of potential implications for employment, livelihoods, but also equity, justice, and biodiversity. Much depends upon the purpose of the food system or territory, but there is contestation on potential food futures at different scales. There are increasing calls for systemic levers, but barriers to action are significant.

The Transformative Change for Biodiversity and Equity (TCforBE) project, (2022 – 2026), will support transdisciplinary research to co-generate transformative change pathways in the context of telecoupled agrifood systems. It will engage diverse stakeholders and explore plural perspectives within the EU and partner countries of Cameroon, Colombia, and Kenya, including EU and national policymakers and Indigenous Peoples and local communities. The project aims to strengthen stakeholder capacity on transformative change pathways leading to enhanced biodiversity and equity outcomes.

Underpinned by multi-stakeholder social learning cycles and attention to plural values, the researchers will seek to co-generate and co-analyse transformative change pathways at different scales for highly telecoupled landscapes and to facilitate dialogues between landscape actors and national and EU scales. To inform these learning cycles and dialogues, researcher driven activities will enrich the landscape and national learning processes and contribute to an overall analysis of transformative change pathways in telecoupled contexts. Envisaged research and learning activities include:

- Conceptual work on transformative change and biodiversity and equity pathways in telecoupled food and agriculture contexts, and synthesis and analysis of findings.
- Exploration of plural perspectives on transformative change at EU, national and landscape scales through qualitative research.
- Social learning cycles at landscape scale: participant-driven learning to co-generate transformative change pathways for food systems and territories (creative learning activities) and to inform/reflect upon planned researcher-led activities (e.g. rural imaginaries research, Bayesian tool development, case studies of corporate and regenerative enterprises). Analysis and social learning on plural perspectives on transformative change at national scale and identification of land use change drivers (e.g. commodity impacts, at-risk biodiversity hotspots, and sustainable landscape initiative impacts).
- A global dialogue, facilitated by the Global Landscapes Forum, will link the transdisciplinary processes between the scales, supported by additional dissemination and communication activities.
- Generation of scenarios and modelling of EU agrofood systems transformations.
- Analysis of interconnected processes and levers including EU biodiversity governance, trade, legal, consumer, collective action and sustainable finance levers and social innovations.

Background

There are seven work packages (WPs) addressing the project's specific objectives, each with associated results and deliverables. WP7 concerns management, dissemination, and communication of the project. All work packages will engage with communications. WP7 has a particular focus on making the knowledge, tools and methods generated by the project available to global audiences through appropriate media, to inform policy dialogues and learning. The transformative change pathways for landscape approaches, will be shared with and disseminated to policymakers, researchers, and agro-food system stakeholders.

TCforBE overall approach.

The overall approach is underpinned by **multi-stakeholder social learning cycles** and ensuring attention is given to plural values. The researchers will seek to cogenerate and co-analyse transformative change pathways at different scales for highly telecoupled landscapes and to facilitate dialogues between landscape actors and national and EU level stakeholders.

To inform these learning cycles and dialogues, researcher driven activities will enrich the landscape and national level learning processes and contribute to an overall analysis of transformative change pathways in telecoupled contexts (Figure 1).

Figure 1.

Figure 1 Components of the TCforBE Project

The envisaged research and learning activities include:

- Conceptual work on transformative change and biodiversity and equity pathways in telecoupled food and agriculture contexts, and synthesis and analysis of findings.
- Generation of scenarios and modelling of EU agrofood systems transformations. Understanding the potential implications of EU policy and societal transitions for low- and middle-income countries that link to the EU through telecoupling is vital as dietary shifts are already occurring and policy decisions are being made which may reduce or change EU country sourcing patterns.
- Exploration of plural perspectives on transformative change at EU, national and landscape scales (see Table 1) through qualitative research.
- Analysis of interconnected processes and levers including EU biodiversity governance, trade, legal, consumer, collective action and sustainable finance levers and social innovations.)
- Analysis and social learning on plural perspectives on transformative change at national scale and identification of land use change drivers (e.g. commodity impacts, at-risk biodiversity hotspots, and sustainable landscape initiative impacts.)
- Social learning cycles at landscape scale (see three landscapes* in Table 1): participant-driven learning to co-generate transformative change pathways for food systems and territories (creative learning activities) and to inform/reflect upon planned researcher-led activities.
- A global dialogue, facilitated by the Global Landscapes Forum, will link the transdisciplinary processes between the scales, supported by additional dissemination and communication activities.

Table 1: The Study Producer Countries and Landscapes

Country	Landscapes	Landscape characteristics & telecoupled agri-food commodities
Cameroon	*Dja-Tridom	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High biodiversity forested landscape with conservation area: Dja Biosphere Reserve, with indigenous ethnic groups Increasing trade in cocoa, timber, non-timber forest products (NTFP), oil palm (national & local trade) Encroachment, fragmentation, and degradation of Dja Biosphere Reserve, restrictions to customary use by Baka ethnic groups, illegal logging, ivory and bushmeat hunting, increased infrastructure, mining and agro-plantations (rubber, oil palm) Conservation & Sustainable landscape initiatives: Dja Green cocoa landscape and Roadmap to deforestation free cocoa; REDD in Southern humid forested plateau (ERP1); Forum of Dja Actors; Synergy Platform between Ngoyla-Mintom Actors (SYAMINGO); Technical Operational Units (TOUs); Model Forests. Medium-high levels of telecoupling cocoa to EU
Colombia	*Magdalena Department, Santa Marta	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High biodiversity from sea, dry tropical forest remnants to Sierra Nevada foothills Long history agricultural expansion for banana, cocoa and oil palm export trade Violence, illicit economies, labour equity and working conditions, and weak state presence. Conservation projects & Sustainable landscape initiatives: Cesar, Huila and Magdalena, Colombia PPI compacts with IDH; SAN, ISEAL & Swiss State Secretariat Blueprint for Sustainable landscape High levels of telecoupling of cocoa, palm oil, banana and coffee to EU
Kenya	*Mau forest – Masai-Mara river basin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High biodiversity forests, savannah and wetlands with protected and conservation areas, important water catchment area with indigenous ethnic groups, community forests and water users associations Expanding rice and fish farming lower Yala and Nyando Basins, grasslands with grazing systems, highlands tea-avocado-fruit-livestock-timber-NTFP, horticulture local, national and export trade Conservation & Sustainable landscape initiatives : Regenerative, conservation & SLIs: MaMaSe program Medium levels of telecoupling of tea, avocado, horticulture products to EU

*Showing 3 selected landscapes where social learning activities take place.

TCforBE DEC tools

In deliverable 7.7 a set of tailored DEC tools, materials and activities are being developed. These include dissemination (e.g. peer-reviewed publications, conferences, meetings, participation in conferences), communications (e.g. webpage, social media, templates for policy briefs and press releases, brand elements such as project logo and colour palette etc.). These outputs differ in aims (e.g. some are to inform, to engage or co-create). The DEC tools, materials and activities also serve to grow the TCforBE network and facilitate knowledge sharing on transformative approaches.

The tools described below were developed to help streamline communication and dissemination of results from all the work packages on the project. This will help leverage communication to maximise the potential of TCforBE by ensuring that project findings, results and recommendations are effectively communicated to stakeholders.

Internal project DEC tools

The tools below were set up to encourage good management, communication and collaboration between project partners and to increase the impact of communication overall.

Basecamp

Basecamp, an online project management and data storage tool was set up at the kick off of the project (month 0). It is the main mechanism for storing and accessing internal project information. It holds information on project updates, events schedule, outputs and communication tools like templates (for press releases, briefing papers, presentations etc.), and brand guidelines. It also features a message board to facilitate quick and easy information exchange within and across teams on the project.

Figure 2: Screenshot of the Basecamp interface

Calendar of workshops and meetings

A Gantt chart (excel sheet) was set up at the kick off of the project (month 0) and provides simple calendar with the dates of planned meetings – for the whole project team and sub sections of the team. This tool helps to avoid overlap and keep partners aware of events. It also lists deliverables and project milestones.

DEC activities tracking tool

A tracking list was developed using Microsoft Excel to maintain an updated record of project communication and dissemination activities. This enhances tracking of all communications and dissemination activities across the project for reporting, helping to streamline TCforBE communications and publicity. The tool is available to use for all project partners.

Internal presentations

Regular presentations were made (during the quarterly project meetings) to popularise the project communications strategy, highlight and agree on action points. This ensures that the project team remains abreast with TCforBE DEC obligations and the latest DEC developments on the project. These activities also provide a platform for feedback to improve management, dissemination and communication on the project.

Glossary of definitions

The TCforBE project transdisciplinary glossary is a collection of transdisciplinary terms to guide the multi and transdisciplinary work on the project. It shared internally on Basecamp and is posted on Zenodo given that with other EU Horizon Biodiversity projects we agreed to share key definitions. It provides transdisciplinary and plural perspectives on key terms used in the project. The glossary is regularly revised and updated to ensure continued relevance as the project evolves.

Social learning guide

Social learning is part of the overall TCforBE project approach and central to work packages (WPs) 2, 4 and 5. The TCforBE social learning guide explores transdisciplinarity, co-production, participatory action research and multi-stakeholder social learning approaches. It was developed to inform project design particularly in Cameroon, Colombia, and Kenya as part of WPs 2, 4 and 5.

External DEC tools

Brand kit

The TCforBE brand kit is a set of visual assets that define the project's brand identity. It includes the project logo, typography, colour palette and brand guidelines. The kit is a blueprint to maintain consistency across all project communications and promotional materials. TCforBE brand guidelines outline how the project should be presented across all dissemination and communication channels to ensure consistent messaging and visual identity. The guidelines also define the project's vision and audiences in a clear and accessible as shown below:

Vision – To co-generate plural transformative change pathways for telecoupled food and agricultural systems to enhance biodiversity and equity outcomes.

Audience – Local communities, funders (EU), EU policymakers and government departments, other academic organisations and research community related to transformative change, biodiversity and equity.

2.2 BRAND ELEMENTS TOOL-KIT OVERVIEW

Horizontal Brand Logo

Vertical Brand Logo

Colour

Typeface

This typeface is for headings

And this typeface is for sub-headings, secondary body copy and labeling graphs and diagrams.

And we also have this system font typeface for internal digital documents.

Figure 3: Screenshot from project brand kit showing project logo, typeface and colours

PowerPoint template

In line with the project brand guidelines, a PowerPoint presentation template was developed and circulated to all project staff. This was done to ensure brand consistency across the multiple communication and dissemination fora e.g. conferences, workshops, seminars etc. in which project staff would participate. The template incorporates the project logo, brand colours and fonts allowing for easy on-brand editing and adaptation. The template was also shared with the EU and the EU Transformative Change cluster of projects.

Conferences and meetings

Members of the TCforBE team have attended and/or presented at international, regional and local conferences to share their findings, receive feedback on their work on the project, network with other researchers and stay updated on the latest developments in the field of transformative change. Some of the major meetings and conferences attended include the ESG Radboud conference, International Forest Policy Conference and SCORAI ERSCP Wageningen Conference. The team have also contributed to several seminars and meetings, some co-organised with the EU transformative change cluster projects. We will continue to seek out relevant conferences to participate in and /or present results at throughout the project lifetime.

Publications

Peer reviewed publications are a major channel through which TCforBE researchers disseminate their findings, recommendations and lessons learnt through their work on the project. This makes project results broadly available, facilitates intellectual exchange in the research community and enhances the impact of the project. TCforBE researchers publish their work in open access journals in line with EU open access requirements. The publications are also available on Zenodo, (an EU open research repository). on various transformative change themes.

Policy briefs

Four policy briefs have been developed to translate project research into actionable insights, support evidence-informed decisions, influence policy debates and agendas and strengthen TCforBE's legitimacy and visibility. The briefs provide insights on transformative legal pathways for biodiversity conservation, biodiversity finance, accounting and regulation, and leverage points for tackling unsustainable value chains. More policy briefs are being developed as more research results are obtained. The policy briefs are all available on Zenodo.

Project leaflet

The project leaflet provides a summary of the TCforBE project, its aims and objectives and expected research and learning activities. It also defines the main areas (producer countries and landscapes) where project activities are focussed. It is a useful resource presenting a synopsis of the project clearly and succinctly making it easy to describe the project's relevance to stakeholders. The leaflet was also translated into other international languages like French and Spanish to facilitate its use especially in partner countries where these languages are predominantly used.

Website

The project now has a [website](#) as a dedicated platform to disseminate knowledge, showcase and promote research findings and facilitate collaboration.

A [project webpage](#) was previously established on the Wageningen University website at the start of the project. The webpage was an important source of information on project activities and has sections covering the project, 'partners', 'publications', 'news', and 'resources'. Public project deliverables were published on the webpage, as well as on Zenodo and social media.

However, there was a critical gap, the lack of a website as a central repository of insights and knowledge generated on the project, and to accommodate the evolving demands of the project. Due to its single page scope, the WU webpage was limiting the range of communication from the project.

The website now enables a much broader range of information (including deliverables, results and recommendations) and functionality to be presented and accessed by TCforBE stakeholders and provide a more comprehensive user experience.

Figure 4: The new TCforBE website

Social media

Social media offers an important platform for the project to engage with relevant communities and share findings, lessons learnt and recommendations with a wider audience. This helps the project to build and strengthen key networks with other researchers and increase the reach and impact of the work on the project. The project team initially opted for researchers to post updates of their work on their institutional and/or personal social media platforms using dedicated hashtags like #tc4be, #TcforBE #Transformative Change, #biodiversity and #equity. However, as the project evolves and approaches a stage where most of the teams are getting results on their specific deliverables, a change of approach was deemed necessary. A project LinkedIn page was therefore set up in November 2024. The page has garnered close to 300 followers in its first year and will be the central social media publicity point for all project news and results. The page further accentuates the project's online identity and enhances its overall image.

In line with the above objectives, joint social media campaigns were conducted with 11 other EU-Horizon cluster projects for example the International Biodiversity Day (IBD) campaign which ran from Earth Day (22 April) to IBD (22 May). This helped further raise the profile of TCforBE's work and that of the wider EU-Horizon transformative change portfolio of research projects. It also helped link and highlight the relevance of the project's work to international and regional biodiversity-related events.

Figure 5: Screenshot of TCforBE LinkedIn page

Press release template

A template and guidelines were produced for project press releases to guarantee a format that fits journalists' requirements. This enables project partners to easily draft press releases highlighting particular project activities, developments or results or key project events/initiatives while maintaining brand consistency.

Summary

In this report, we have highlighted tools, materials and activities developed to facilitate Dissemination, Education and Communication (DEC) efforts on the TCforBE project. The resources described are important for facilitating internal and external communication, collaboration, knowledge exchange and overall project management. They have been classified into two groups; the first consisting resources with an internal focus (to streamline team communication, collaboration and co-creation) and the second consisting resources intended to facilitate engagement with stakeholders external to the project.

